

MODEL2BIO. Modelling tool for giving value to agri-food residual streams in bio-based industries

T. Fernández-Arévalo¹, M. Mendiola², A. Podhorski³, L. Sijtsma⁴, E. Maron⁵, L. Papista⁶, M. Diaz⁷, M. Uyttebroek⁸, M. Obermeier⁹, K.G. Sakellariou¹⁰

¹CEIT-Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Paseo Manuel Lardizabal 15, 20018 Donostia - San Sebastián, Spain.

²Agri-food Technology Center Cita, Carretera Nacional 120, km 22,8., 26315 Alesón, La Rioja, Spain

³Universidad de Navarra, Tecnun, Paseo Manuel Lardizabal 13, 20018 Donostia - San Sebastián, Spain.

⁴Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Food & Biobased Research, Bornse Weilanden 9, 6708 WG Wageningen, The Netherlands

⁵Celabor, Avenue du parc 38, 4650 – Chaineux, Belgium

⁶Clube - Cluster of Bioeconomy and Environment of Western Macedonia, ZEP area, Kozani 50100

⁷FOOD+i - Clúster Alimentario del Valle del Ebro / Polígono Tejerías Norte – c/ Los Huertos, 2 / 26500 Calahorra, La Rioja

⁸Flanders' FOOD, Wetenschapstraat 14A, 1040 Brussels, Belgium.

⁹European Science Communication Institute (ESCI), Lindenstasse 87, 26123 Oldenburg, Germany

¹⁰DIADYMA SA, Waste Management of Western Macedonia, 6th km Kozani-Ptolemaida Rd., GR-50150, Kozani, Greece

Corresponding author: tfernandez@ceit.es

ABSTRACT

The agri-food industry generates around 50% of global waste, of which only 36% is recycled, although the potential recovery could be as high as 60%. These residual streams can be used as feedstock for the bio-based industry (BBI), provided that the composition, logistics and volume are carefully analysed. Within the framework of the European Model2Bio project (H2020-BBI-JTI-2019. No 887191), the authors are developing a Decision Support System (DSS) tool for the management of residual streams produced in agri-food companies. This will be an innovative concept that using predictive models will be able to select the best routes for valorising these streams considering their composition, seasonality, and industry location, among other factors. This innovative MODEL2BIO-DSS tool is based on the interconnection of three complementary elements (simulation module, optimisation algorithm and LCA module).

The main advantage of the tool is the possibility of giving a holistic solution or prioritisation. Although there are many commercial programs for the simulation of industrial processes, these are mainly based on the analysis of specific facilities, and not on broader analyses with various industries, in which logistics plays a key role. Model2Bio will simulate the entire value chain providing recommendations from a holistic perspective (technical, economic, environmental and social), with the prioritisation of the valorisation possibilities through technical-economic criteria and the final decision through holistic criteria. Within the framework of the Model2Bio project, the tool is being tested in 3 European areas (Spain, Greece, Belgium) with the aim of analysing different management systems, with different degrees of development of valorisation technologies. To show the potential of this new concept for waste management, the final work will present the analysis and optimisation of the agri-food residual streams valorisation in La Rioja (Spain) carried out with the Model2Bio-DSS tool. In this analysis, a comparison of the current agri-food residual streams management and the optimised management will be presented, considering economic and holistic aspects.

Keywords

Agri-food residual stream valorisation, Bio-based industries (BBIs), Decision Support System (DSS) tool, Waste management and optimisation.

MODEL2BIO. Modelling tool for giving value to agri-food residual streams in bio-based industries

T. Fernández-Arévalo¹, M. Mendiola², A. Podhorski³, L. Sijtsma⁴, E. Maron⁵, L. Papista⁶, M. Diaz⁷, M. Uyttebroek⁸, M. Obermeier⁹, K.G. Sakellariou¹⁰

¹CEIT-Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Paseo Manuel Lardizabal 15, 20018 Donostia - San Sebastián, Spain.

²Agri-food Technology Center Cita, Carretera Nacional 120, km 22,8., 26315 Alesón, La Rioja, Spain

³Universidad de Navarra, Tecnun, Paseo Manuel Lardizabal 13, 20018 Donostia - San Sebastián, Spain.

⁴Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Food & Biobased Research, Bornse Weilanden 9, 6708 WG Wageningen, The Netherlands

⁵Celabor, Avenue du parc 38, 4650 – Chaineux, Belgium

⁶Clube - Cluster of Bioeconomy and Environment of Western Macedonia, ZEP area, Kozani 50100

⁷FOOD+i - Clúster Alimentario del Valle del Ebro / Polígono Tejerías Norte – c/ Los Huertos, 2 / 26500 Calahorra, La Rioja

⁸Flanders' FOOD, Wetenschapstraat 14A, 1040 Brussels, Belgium.

⁹European Science Communication Institute (ESCI), Lindenstasse 87, 26123 Oldenburg, Germany

¹⁰DIADYMA SA, Waste Management of Western Macedonia, 6th km Kozani-Ptolemaida Rd., GR-50150, Kozani, Greece

Corresponding author: tfernandez@ceit.es

INTRODUCTION

Waste disposal/processing is the major challenge for our society. In 2018, the total waste generated in the EU-27 amounted to 2.277 million tons, of which only 88 million tonnes corresponded to unavoidable food supply chain wastes from farm to fork, and food wastes in the later stages of the supply chain (retail and households). One of the aims of the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy is to define strategies to reduce waste by 30% in 2025 and by 50% in 2030. In addition, EU waste policy aims to contribute to the circular economy by extracting value-added resources from waste as much as possible, minimising the final generation of waste. In this framework, agri-food residual streams are a potential substitute for fossil-based resources and have an important added value, if these streams are used as feedstock in bio-based industries (BBIs). However, most organic residual streams present a high complexity and a heterogeneous mixture, which make the production and separation of specific compounds difficult. Furthermore, the variability in quantities and physico-chemical composition of these streams, as well as their seasonality limit the technological and economic feasibility of the conversion processes to valuable products. Therefore, a deeper knowledge of the composition, logistics, volume and valorisation potential of organic residual streams could support the decision-making process to maximise the benefit of a specific raw material and select the most appropriate technologies for its optimal recovery.

The objective of this work is to present a Decision Support System (DSS) tool for the management of residual streams produced by agri-food companies. This tool is being developed within the framework of the European MODEL2BIO (<https://www.model2bio.eu/>) project (H2020-BBI-JTI-2019. No 887191). This tool is an innovative concept that, through predictive models, allows selecting the best routes for valorising these streams considering their composition, seasonality, and industry location among other factors.

MODEL2BIO-DSS TOOL

The tool has a holistic perspective for, the selection or prioritisation of the valorisation routes taking into account a technical, economic, environmental and social aspects. Firstly, the tool performs a technical/economic prioritisation to select the best valorisation options, and later, these priorities are analysed from a general environmental, social and economic perspective.

Based on basic information about agri-food companies, the tool is capable of predicting which is the best way to valorise food by-products, estimating in turn the type and quantity of bio-products produced, the energy generated, the net operational costs of the entire value chain, and the waste generated, among several other aspects (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the Model2Bio-DSS tool

This MODEL2BIO-DSS tool is based on the interconnection of 3 complementary elements: Simulation Module, Optimisation Algorithm and LCA module.

Simulation Module

The Simulation Module is able to predict the mass fluxes for any bio-based residual stream alternative using a set of compatible model libraries describing the agri-food production lines, the intermediate processes (storage, mixing, separation and transport) and the final valorisation in the bioprocesses. All libraries use the same Components Vector according to the Plant-Wide Modelling (PWM) methodology (Grau *et al.*, 2007). The PWM methodology is a systematic and rigorous methodology for constructing mathematical models able to describe the whole systems as complex as required in each case study. This approach facilitates the mass, electric charge (proton balance) and energy continuity throughout the whole system.

- The Production Line Models of the agri-food industry are a set of mathematical models for the description of the food production lines. The output of this library are the physiochemical characteristics of residual streams based on its composition, and the flow of the residual stream generated for each kg of product, using the inputs uploaded by the user to the tool.
- The Intermediate Process models describe the transformations of the residual streams to BBI feedstocks, and include storage and transport and, biological processes such as fermentations or physico-chemical processes such as micro-wave stabilisation.
- The Bio-processes models describe the BBI processes, in which the residual streams can be valorised. In this set of models, all possible biochemical processes are considered for valorising the agri-food residual streams, such as (solid-state) fermentations, anaerobic digestion and extraction processes. This library will be easily expandable for including other technologies when needed.

Optimisation algorithm

The Optimisation algorithm is able to select automatically the bio-based residual stream alternatives that minimise a global cost function previously defined using the mathematical models constructed.

Life Cycle Assessment Module

Finally, the LCA module estimates the environmental, economic and social impacts associated with any bio-based residual stream alternative using an LCA methodology.

CASE STUDY

Within the framework of the Model2Bio project, the tool is being tested in 3 European areas (Spain, Greece, Belgium) with the aim of analysing different management systems, with different degrees of development of valorisation technologies. In this work, the case study focuses on the analysis and optimisation of the agri-food residual streams valorisation in La Rioja (Spain). In the final work, the base situation or current situation will be compared with the optimisation provided by the tool (Figure 2a).

Figure 2. Area selected for study; a) example of the potential of the DSS tool, and b) companies identified in the analysis area.

The steps for analysis are as follows:

- (1) Identification of companies in the area (Figure 2b).
- (2) Estimate of production of each company (Figure 2b).
- (3) Identification of the BBIs (incorporation of general information).
- (4) Analysis and prioritisation.

POTENTIAL AND USEFULNESS OF THE TOOL

The tool can offer different advantages depending on its role in the value chain.

AGRI-FOOD COMPANIES

- To increase the knowledge about the potential of their agri-food residual streams.
- Find new ways to add value to residual streams.

WASTE MANAGEMENT COMPANIES

- To increase income and business opportunities by providing new ways of handling agri-food residual streams.

BIO-INDUSTRIES

- To identify new markets: new processes, new by-products.
- To optimise their processes through a greater knowledge of the availability of by-products and the effect of introducing new by-products.

CONCLUSIONS

Simulation tools are valuable instruments that allow optimisation of systems and the selection of alternatives in an agile and simple way. A comparative analysis of the most appropriate valorisation options for the La Rioja area using the Model2Bio-DSS tool will be presented and discussed. The potential that this tool offers for the different actors in the value chain will be highlighted.

REFERENCES

- Grau P., de Gracia M., Vanrolleghem P.A. and Ayesa E. (2007). A new plant-wide modelling methodology for WWTPs. *Water Research*, 41, 4357-4372.